

Teachers' Compliance with Professional Ethics and Their Enhanced Productivity in Lagos State Public Senior Secondary Schools Education District I, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in Lagos State public senior secondary schools Education District I, Nigeria. Disproportionate Sampling technique was used in selecting 15 public secondary schools in Education District I. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 12 teachers, one principal and two vice-principals of each school selected making a total of 225 respondents. A descriptive Survey research design and correlation, data were collected through a questionnaire titled Teacher Compliance Professional Ethics and Teachers Productivity (TCPETP) with face and content validity and was subjected to a test re-test reliability method with 0.72 reliability coefficient. The study found that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment at ($r = 0.562$, p -value 0.000); teachers' punctuality have significant influence at ($r = 0.534$, p -value 0.000); teachers' confidentiality significantly influences ($r = 0.560$, p -value 0.001); teachers' integrity significantly influences at ($r = 0.531$, p -value 0.000) and teachers' communication significantly influences at ($r = 0.372$, p -value 0.000) teachers' productivity and that teachers' dress sense do not significantly influence teachers' productivity ($r = 0.079$, p -value 0.238); The study therefore concludes that there is a relationship between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools. It was recommended that schools should establish mentorship programs where experienced teachers with high integrity can guide and support less experienced teachers, promoting a culture of ethical behavior, organize workshops and seminars aimed at improving teachers' communication skills, including both verbal and non-verbal communication, develop and enforce clear dress code policies that promote a professional appearance for teachers, implement recognition and reward programs to acknowledge and celebrate teachers' commitment and dedication.

Keywords: Teachers' Compliance, Professional Ethics, and Teacher Productivity.

Introduction

The development of a nation makes the role of teachers very important in the school. This is because there is no country whether developed or developing that does not require the service of the teachers. The development of any nation depends upon the amount of educated individual that has quality education. Education is the most veritable tool for achieving all round development in any country. This justifies why Omoto (2020) opined that if you see any society that is not performing well, search out what is spent on education. The increase in national income and per capital income is a work of education and that gap among nations can better be explained on human capacity rather than physical capacity. The school prepares its young ones for the management of the nation's economy. It passes the desired and acceptable practices, behaviors, values, norms of the society to the students. The school has the responsibility of making sure that its products are found worthy both in character and in learning. Therefore, for any educational institutions to achieve its success and goals, it depends on the teachers' commitment. Teachers are regarded as the strongest pillar of the society. Also, one can submit that, teacher is like a potter who delicately shapes our impressionable minds, a vessel that defines our perception and ambitions. In the light of this, there should

be provision of high-quality teachers who have good academic knowledge of their subject disciplines and who possess professional skills, experience, administrative responsibility, attitudes and values as well as personal qualities for effective teaching. More so, teachers in term of quality are expected to function in some other duty to help enhancing the performance of the student. (Gbesoevi, 2019)

School leadership demands a pragmatic approach by focusing on results and consequences in the application of rules, procedures and position as leaders, in order to achieve educational goals. Some school principals' unethical conducts hamper the management of schools for goal attainment. Some of the school principals lack integrity; they engage and encourage examination malpractice. Some do not preserve and facilitate harmonious working relationship amongst school members, while some misappropriate school funds. Their behaviours do not reflect the school values neither do the decisions they take based on statutory and legal framework. Some do not follow due process in administering discipline (Skefkovics & Shapiro, 2018). They make speedy decisions without checking the legal and regulatory clauses that are involved. School leadership demands ennobling conduct as it is through the school that morals are inculcated to the students. The inability of school principals to ensure that their conducts coincide with the school ethics constitute serious threat to the administration of public senior secondary schools for goal attainment (Celik, 2020).

Today, work ethics becomes a prerequisite for conducting any type of business, particularly in the global market place since every business organization operates with multiple relationship including stakeholders such as customers, employees, suppliers, investors amongst others who perhaps would prefer their company to be ethical (Azmi, 2016). Building a strong ethical culture is also integral to the reputation, growth, and finances of any organization and it helps to build trust among the stakeholders (Azmi, 2016). Ethics are set of principles and values that guide organizations in their decisions, programmes and policies. Work ethics dimensions in organizations include trustworthiness, integrity, accountability and civility (Odu & Akhigbe, 2018); honesty, integrity, fairness, and concern for others (Toor & Ofori, 2019). Employees want to be associated with managers that are honest, credible, respectful, and fair (Collins, 2021) and organizations can achieve better employee attraction and retention when employees have the opportunity to work for truly responsible and ethical employers and this improves employee commitment (Upadhyay & Singh, 2020; Collins, 2021).

Workplace best practices are defined as practices that have been shown to improve an organization's capacity to effectively attract, select, hire, develop, and retain higher performing manpower. Best practices are methods or techniques that are known to consistently produce optimal and efficient result. Kamat (2016), stated that a happy workplace is a huge asset. In such places something happens that transcends policies and practices. Workplace is not what the organizations are doing; it is what their leaders are doing. Best workplace practices include the day-to-day relationship that the employees experience, and not a catalog of policies, programmes and benefits. Best practices represent the most efficient course of action in a particular setting or scenario. (Jennifer & Ashley 2022).

At its core, teachers' compliance with professional ethics is grounded in fundamental values such as honesty, integrity, respect, and fairness (Campbell, 2019). More so, the need to continuously initiate professional ethic among teachers as a program becomes a matter of necessity. Teacher education is a programme that is related to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein. (Gbesoevi et.al. 2022). Honesty entails providing accurate information to students and stakeholders, maintaining transparency in communication, and upholding truthfulness in all professional dealings. Integrity involves adhering to moral principles and ethical standards even in challenging situations, thereby fostering trust and credibility. Respect necessitates recognizing the dignity, rights, and perspectives of all individuals within the educational community, regardless of differences in background or beliefs. Equally too, one can state that fairness requires ensuring equity and impartiality in the treatment of students, promoting inclusive practices, and addressing inequalities.

In the context of public senior secondary schools, where students are navigating the complexities of adolescence and preparing for higher education or the workforce, the role of teachers in modeling ethical behavior becomes particularly significant. Adolescents are highly attuned to ethical considerations and moral exemplars, and teachers serve as influential role models who shape students' attitudes, values, and ethical reasoning (Strike, 2020). By embodying professional ethics in their actions and interactions, teachers not only uphold the integrity of the teaching profession but also contribute to the moral and character development of their students.

Moreover, teachers' compliance with professional ethics is closely intertwined with their effectiveness and productivity in the classroom. Research suggests that teachers who adhere to ethical principles are more likely to create supportive and inclusive learning environments, establish positive relationships with students, and promote academic integrity (Campbell, 2019). Equally too over-politicisation of the process, lack of or poor policy framework guidelines, non-involvement of educational planners among others could bring about non-compliance to professional ethics in school (Gbesoevi & Ola,

2021). Ethical conduct enhances teacher-student rapport, fosters mutual respect, and cultivates a sense of trust and safety conducive to learning. Furthermore, teachers who prioritize ethical considerations are better equipped to navigate ethical dilemmas, resolve conflicts, and make principled decisions in their professional practice.

Moreover, despite the importance of professional ethics in teaching, educators may encounter various challenges and pressures that can impede their ability to maintain ethical standards consistently. Factors such as time constraints, workload demands, institutional policies, and societal expectations may create tensions between ethical ideals and practical realities (Campbell, 2019). Additionally, teachers may face ethical dilemmas related to issues such as academic integrity, student discipline, confidentiality, and cultural sensitivity, requiring ethical reflection and decision-making skills. In light of these complexities, understanding the factors influencing teachers' compliance with professional ethics is essential for promoting ethical conduct and enhancing teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. By identifying the barriers to ethical practice and the supports needed to foster ethical behavior, educators, policymakers, and stakeholders can develop targeted interventions and professional development initiatives to promote a culture of ethical excellence within educational institutions.

In the realm of public senior secondary education, the intersection between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and their productivity presents a multifaceted challenge deserving of investigation. According to Gbesoevi (2022), It is an issue that has attracted a great deal of attention and concern from educators, teachers, parents, learners and the public at large owing to the state of insecurity confronting schools and the general society. More so, the poor productivity of teachers can lead to inadequate student achievement (Gbesoevi et al 2023). Despite the recognised importance of professional ethics in guiding teachers' conduct and shaping the educational environment, there exists a gap in understanding how adherence to ethical standards influences teacher productivity within this specific context. This study aims to address this gap by examining the relationship between teachers' compliance with professional ethics and their productivity in public senior secondary schools.

The problem at hand encompasses several dimensions. Firstly, while professional ethics serve as guiding principles for teachers, the extent to which educators adhere to these standards and the impact of such adherence on their productivity remain underexplored. Secondly, the unique challenges and contextual factors present in public senior secondary schools, including diverse student populations, resource constraints, and societal expectations, may influence teachers' ability to maintain ethical conduct while fulfilling their professional responsibilities. Understanding how these factors intersect with teachers' productivity is essential for informing strategies to promote ethical excellence and optimize educational outcomes.

Furthermore, ethical dilemmas and tensions may arise in the day-to-day practice of teaching, requiring educators to navigate complex moral terrain. Balancing ethical considerations with instructional demands, administrative requirements, and student needs poses challenges that may affect teachers' effectiveness and well-being. Additionally, the role of school actors, institutional culture, and professional development initiatives in supporting teachers' ethical growth and enhancing productivity warrants investigation.

Objective of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I.

Specifically, the study set out to achieve the following objectives which is to:

1. Investigate the influence of teacher's commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
2. Find out the influence of teachers' punctuality on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
3. Examine the influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
4. Determine the influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
5. Assess the influence of teachers' communication on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
6. Establish the influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Questions

The following Research Questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Is there any influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
2. Will teachers' punctuality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
3. Does teachers' confidentiality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
4. Can teachers' integrity have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
5. How does teachers' communication have influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?
6. To what extent does teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses were tested for the study:

1. Teachers' commitment does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
2. Teachers' punctuality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
3. Teachers' confidentiality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
4. Teachers' integrity does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
5. Teachers' communication skills do not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.
6. Teachers dress sense does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive research design using quantitative approach. This involves analysing teachers' compliance with professional ethics and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools. The population of the study consist of all teachers' and principal s in all public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Educational District I comprises of 3 zones which include; Agege, Alimosho, and Ifako Ijaye. The number of senior secondary teachers in Education District I is 1702 teachers and 41 principals. The sample size for this study consists of 180 teachers, 15 principals, and 30 vice principle selected from the population. Disproportionate Sampling technique was used in selecting Five schools from three zones Agege, Alimosho and Ifako-Ijaye respectively. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 12 teachers, One principal Two vice-principals from each 16 sampled school. A self-designed instrument titled "Teacher Compliance Professional Ethics and Teachers Productivity (TCPETP)" was utilised to gather data for the study. Its two aspects were intended to elicit answers to research questions and test the hypotheses. Two sections made up the instrument: Section A collected respondents' personal information, while Sections B contained eighteen items each dimension connected to the variables under investigation and was scaled and scored - Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3), and Strongly Agree were the available response options. Face and content validity was adopted for the instrument in this study. More so, the reliability of the instrument was assessed utilising the test-retest reliability tests, which provided coefficients of 0.72. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and simple percentages was used to analysed demographic data while inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment correlation (PPMC), was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 significant level through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.

Presentations of Results

This chapter presents the results from the data analysis based on the research questions and stated hypotheses for the study. The results were interpreted and each of the hypotheses was either rejected or not rejected at 0.05 level of significance. The first section presents the analysis of data, while the second section presents the summary of findings.

Demographic Data of Respondents

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of respondents on the basis of Gender

Variables		N	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	102	53.3
	Female	123	54.7
Age	29 years below	65	28.8
	30 - 39 years	82	36.4
	40 – 49 years	35	15.5
	50 – 59 years	29	12.8
	60 years above	14	6.2
Educational Qualification	HND/PGDE	28	12.4
	B.Sc/ B.Sc/Ed	180	82
	M.Ed/M.Sc/PGDE	9	4
	PhD	4	1.7
Years of Working Experience	1 – 5	69	31.4
	6 - 10	77	34.2
	11 – 15 years	51	22.6
	16 years and above	184	82
Marital Status	Married	28	12.4
	Singled	5	2.2
	Divorced	4	1.7
	Separated	4	1.7
	Widow		

Source: Field Work 2024

The Table 1 shows that 53.6% of respondents were males while 54.7% of respondents are females. This implies that more female students participated in the study than their male counterparts. From Table 2, 28.8% of the respondents were below 30 years; 36.4% were between the age of 31-40; 15.5% were between the age of 41-50; 12.8% were between the age of 51-60, while the remaining 6.2% were 61 and above. From Table 3, 12.4% of the respondents have NCE/HND; 82% of the respondents have B.Ed. /B.Sc.; 9% of the respondents have M.Ed. /M.Sc.; 4% have other qualification. From Table 4, 12.4% of the respondents fall below 5 years; 31.4% fall between 6-10years; 34.2% fall between 11-15years, while 22.6% were above 15 years. From Table 5, 82% of the respondents are married; 12.4% are single; 2.2% are divorced; 1.7% is separated, while the remaining 1.7% was widow.

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question One: Is there any influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.6: Influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	Teachers demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility towards meeting the educational goals and objectives of the school.	44 19.6%	92 40.9%	60 26.7%	29 12.9%
2	Teachers maintain open and effective communication with students, parents, and colleagues.	40 17.8%	92 40.9%	60 26.7%	29 12.9%
3	Teachers collaborate with colleagues to share resources and best practices for enhancing student learning.	75 33.3%	70 31.1%	40 17.8%	40 17.8%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.6 shows that 60.5% of respondents agree that teachers demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility towards meeting the educational goals and objectives of the school while 39.5% disagree; 58.7% respondents agree that teachers maintain open and effective communication with students, parents and colleagues while 41.3% disagree; 64.4% of respondents agree that teachers collaborate with colleagues to share resources and best practices for enhancing student learning while 35.6% of respondents disagree with the statement. This means that overall, teachers' commitment significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Two: Will teachers' punctuality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.7: Teachers' punctuality has any influence on teachers' productivity

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	Teachers who are punctual are able to manage their classroom time more effectively, leading to increased student learning.	62 27.6%	71 31.6%	52 23.1%	40 17.8%
2	Teacher's punctuality affects their ability to prepare effectively for lessons	65 28.9%	97 43.1%	33 14.7%	30 13.3%
3	Teacher's tardiness affects the overall learning environment in the classroom	11 49.3%	68 30.2%	26 11.6%	20 8.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.7 shows that 59.2% of respondents agree that teachers who are punctual are able to manage their classroom time more effectively, leading to increased student learning while 40.8% disagree; 72.0% of respondents agree that teacher's punctuality affect their ability to prepare effectively for lessons while 22.0% disagree; 79.5% of respondents agree that teacher's tardiness affect the overall learning environment in the classroom while 20.5% disagree. This implies that to a very high extent; teachers' punctuality has a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Three: Does teachers' confidentiality have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.8: Influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
1	I feel more comfortable trying new teaching methods if I know my performance evaluations will be kept confidential.	60 26.7%	58 25.8%	52 23.1%	58 25.8%
2	When I know feedback on my teaching is confidential, I am more likely to openly discuss challenges with school administrators.	68 30.2%	77 34.2%	44 19.6%	36 16.0%
3	If I am concerned about negative evaluations being shared with others, I am less motivated to put in extra effort for lesson planning and student support.	98 43.6%	58 25.8%	17 7.6%	52 23.1%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.8 shows that 52.5% of respondents agree that they feel more comfortable trying new teaching methods if I know my performance evaluations will be kept confidential while 47.5% disagree; 64.4% agree that when they know feedback on their teaching is confidential, they are more likely to openly discuss challenges with school administrators while 35.6% disagree with the statement; 69.4% of respondents agree that if they are concerned about negative evaluations being shared with others, they are less motivated to put in extra effort for lesson planning and student support while 30.6% disagree with the statement. This implies that teachers' confidentiality has a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Four: Can teachers' integrity have any influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.9: Influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity

	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	The integrity of teachers positively influences the school's overall environment.	57 25.3%	111 49.3%	40 17.8%	17 7.6%
2	Teachers demonstrate honesty and transparency in their interactions with colleagues.	66 29.3%	73 32.4%	38 16.9%	48 21.3%
3	Teacher integrity plays a significant role in shaping students' character.	57 25.3%	90 40.0%	31 13.8%	47 20.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.9 shows that 74.6% of respondents agree that the integrity of teachers positively influences the school's overall environment while 25.4% disagree with the statement; 61.7% of respondents agree that teachers demonstrate honesty and transparency in their interactions with colleagues while 37.2% disagree with the statement; 75.3% of respondents agree that teacher integrity plays a significant role in shaping students' character while 24.7% of respondents disagree with the statement. This infers that to a high degree, teachers' integrity have a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Five: How Does Teachers' Communication Have Influence on Teachers' Productivity In Public Senior Secondary School in Lagos State Education District I?

Table 4.10: Influence of Teachers' Communication on Teachers' Productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D
1	Teacher uses a variety of communication methods (e.g., lectures, discussions, activities) to keep the class engaged.	78 34.7%	78 34.7%	39 17.3%	30 13.3%
2	Teacher listens attentively to student questions and responds in a clear and concise manner.	78 34.7%	72 32.0%	45 20.0%	30 13.3%
3	Teacher effectively conveys complex information in a way that is easy to understand.	47 20.9%	84 37.3%	47 20.9%	47 20.9%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.10 shows that 79.4% of respondents agree that teacher uses a variety of communication methods (e.g., lectures, discussions, activities) to keep the class engaged while 20.6% disagree with the statement; 66.7% of respondents agree that teacher listens attentively to student questions and responds in a clear and concise manner while 32.3% were undecided; 58.2% of respondents agree that teacher effectively conveys complex information in a way that is easy to understand while 41.8% disagree with the statement. This implies that overall, teachers' communication have a significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Research Question Six: To what extent does teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I?

Influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity

	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D
1	Students are more likely to be engaged in class when their teacher dresses professionally.	75 33.3%	94 41.8%	33 14.7%	23 10.2%
2	Teachers who dress professionally are perceived as more knowledgeable and authoritative by students.	67 29.8%	115 51.1%	27 12.0%	16 7.1%
3	The overall appearance of a school, including teacher attire, can influence student behavior.	76 33.8%	100 44.4%	40 17.8%	9 4.0%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.11 shows that 75.1% of respondents agree that students are more likely to be engaged in class when their teacher dresses professionally while 24.9% disagree with the statement; 80.9% of respondents agree that teachers who dress professionally are perceived as more knowledgeable and authoritative by students while 19.1% of respondents disagree with the statement; 78.2% of respondents agree that the overall appearance of a school, including teacher attire, can influence student

behavior while 21.8% of respondents disagree with the statement. This means that to a very high extent, teachers' dress sense influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Teachers' commitment does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.12 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' Commitment	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.562**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.12 shows the Pearson correlation result suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' commitment and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.562$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. The null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Two:

Teachers' punctuality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.13 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on teachers' punctuality influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' Punctuality	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' Punctuality	Pearson Correlation	1	.534**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.534**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.13 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' punctuality and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.534$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result implies that teacher's punctuality have significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Three:

Teachers' confidentiality does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.14 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' confidentiality on teachers' productivity

		Teachers' confidentiality	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' confidentiality	Pearson Correlation	1	.560*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.560*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	225	225

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.14 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' confidentiality and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.560$, p -value 0.001). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.001) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result indicates that teachers' confidentiality significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Four:

Teachers' integrity does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.15 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' integrity on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' integrity	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' integrity	Pearson Correlation	1	.531**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.531**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.15 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' integrity and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.531$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result infers that teachers' integrity significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Five

Teachers' communication skills do not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.16 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' communication on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' communication	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' communication	Pearson Correlation	1	.372**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	225	225
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.372**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.16 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' communication and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.372$, p -value 0.000). This relationship is statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. Null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This result means that teachers' communication significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Hypothesis Six:

Teachers dress sense does not have any significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Table 4.17 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the significant influence of teachers' dress sense on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school

		Teachers' dress sense	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' dress sense	Pearson Correlation	1	.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.238
	N	225	224
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.079	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.238	
	N	225	225

Table 4.17 shows the Pearson correlation result which suggests that there is no significant relationship between teachers' dress sense and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.079$, p -value 0.238). This relationship is not statistically significant because the p -value for the result (0.238) is more than the level of significance (0.05) used for the study. The null hypothesis was accepted, while the alternative hypothesis was not accepted. This result establishes that teachers' dress sense do not significantly influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school in Lagos State Education District I.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that there is a significant influence of teachers' commitment on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result aligns with the study of Akpotu, Ojoko, and Egbede (2020) conducted a study on "Teacher Commitment and Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria" and found that teacher commitment had a significant positive impact on teacher productivity, with committed teachers exhibiting higher levels of job satisfaction and student academic achievement.

The study established that teacher's punctuality has significant influence on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result validates the study of Adeniji, Akinwumi, and Olatunbosun (2019) who conducted a study on impact of teachers' punctuality on students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools" and found that teachers'

punctuality significantly influenced students' academic achievement, with punctual teachers recording higher student performance.

The study revealed that teachers' confidentiality significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result coincides with the findings of Adeyemo, Ojedokun and Olowo (2018) who conducted a study on impact of confidentiality on teacher productivity in Nigerian public secondary schools and found that teachers' adherence to confidentiality significantly enhanced their productivity, as it fostered trust and cooperation among colleagues and students. The study showed that teachers' integrity significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result supports the findings of Maaja and Krista (2016), who conducted a study on the importance of integrity: determining factors and some hints to ethics. One of the most important findings of our study is that the assessment of peer's value integrity tells the most how important honest is for the focal person. Results reveal also the role of some other personal values as well as the country of residence in respect with the importance of integrity.

The study revealed that teachers' communication significantly influences teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result coincides with the findings of Huberts (2018) who conducted a study on teachers' communication what it is and why it is important. The study found that integrity is a crucial concept for an understanding of governance. Not as an alternative for "ethics theory and approaches" but to be embedded in existent "approaches" and theory development. In that sense it belongs on the agenda for further progress in these fields of study, in particular in empirical research on the actual significance of integrity and teachers' communication in governance.

The study indicated that teachers' dress sense does not significantly influence teachers' productivity in public senior secondary school. This result supports the findings of Udeh, Nwosu, and Onyia (2018) who investigated teachers' dress code on productivity in Nigerian public secondary schools and established that no significant relationship between teachers' dress sense and productivity, suggesting that other factors such as teacher motivation and school environment play a more critical role in influencing productivity. Ayi and Akhigbe (2018) conducted a study on workplace ethics and teachers' compliance of secondary school in Nigeria. The results indicated that a significant association exists between civility, trustworthiness, integrity and measures of employee commitment, and that culture moderated the influence of workplace ethics and employees' commitment. Based on the study findings, it was concluded that integrity, teachers' compliance, teachers' punctuality, teachers' communication, teachers' confidentiality and teachers' dress sense influences teachers' productivity.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the influence of various factors teachers' commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, communication, and dress sense on the productivity of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I. In conclusion, the study on Teachers' Compliance with Professional Ethics and Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Lagos State has yielded significant insights into the critical role of professional ethics in enhancing teacher productivity. The findings unequivocally establish that teachers' commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, and communication are vital components of professional ethics that substantially influence teacher productivity. The significant influence of teachers' commitment on productivity underscores the importance of teachers' dedication and passion for their profession. Teachers who demonstrate unwavering commitment to their students and the educational process are more likely to exhibit high productivity levels.

Similarly, the positive impact of punctuality on productivity highlights the significance of time management and responsibility in teaching. Teachers who adhere to schedules and timelines contribute to a culture of accountability and efficiency. Confidentiality, integrity, and communication also emerged as essential ethical standards that foster teacher productivity. Teachers who maintain confidentiality, uphold integrity, and communicate effectively with students, colleagues, and parents create a conducive learning environment. Notably, the study revealed that teachers' dress sense does not significantly influence productivity, suggesting that professional attire, while important, is not a primary determinant of teacher effectiveness.

Overall, this study underscores the imperative of professional ethics in promoting teacher productivity and, by extension, quality education. To optimize teacher productivity, educational stakeholders must prioritize the cultivation of professional ethics, providing ongoing training and support for teachers to develop and maintain these essential standards. By doing so, public senior secondary schools in Lagos State can foster a culture of professionalism, accountability, and excellence, ultimately enhancing student outcomes and contributing to the development of a well-educated and productive citizenry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on the influence of various factors on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State Education District I, the following recommendations are proposed

1. Policymakers should integrate professional ethics into teacher education programs and ongoing professional development initiatives, ensuring teachers receive regular training and support. They should also establish clear policies and guidelines for teacher conduct and productivity.
2. School administrators should prioritize the cultivation of professional ethics, fostering a culture of accountability and excellence within schools. Regular workshops and seminars on ethics and productivity should be organized, and teachers' adherence to professional standards should be monitored and evaluated.
3. Teacher training institutions should incorporate comprehensive modules on professional ethics and productivity into their curricula, ensuring prospective teachers understand the importance of commitment, punctuality, confidentiality, integrity, and effective communication.
4. Teachers should strive to internalize and demonstrate professional ethics, recognizing their critical role in promoting productivity and quality education. They should prioritize ongoing professional development, seeking feedback and support to enhance their teaching practices.

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